

Immunomodulatory and ROS-mediated anti-MMP-2/MMP-9 effects of lysine ethyl ester betulinate*

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Abstract

This study examined the anti-invasive, immunomodulatory, and redox-modulating properties of betulinic acid (BA) and its ionic liquid derivative, [LysOEt][BA]₂, in breast cancer and immune cell models. MDA-MB-231 cells were treated with increasing concentrations of BA or [LysOEt][BA]₂ to evaluate intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation and matrix metalloproteinase-2/matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-2/MMP-9) activity. Human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were used to evaluate lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced cytokine responses at the messenger RNA (mRNA) and protein levels. Both compounds induced concentration-dependent oxidative stress; however, [LysOEt][BA]₂ elicited markedly stronger ROS production than BA. A pronounced reduction in intracellular MMP-2 activity, which was more pronounced with [LysOEt][BA]₂, indicated suppression of proteolytic pathways linked to invasiveness. In PBMCs, both BA and the ionic liquid (IL) derivative significantly inhibited IL-6 and TNF-α secretion and reduced IL6 transcription. However, [LysOEt][BA]₂ exhibited a dose-dependent immunosuppressive profile. Overall, [LysOEt][BA]₂ enhanced the anticancer and anti-inflammatory activities of BA, supporting ionic-liquid-based derivatization as a promising strategy for improving triterpene bioactivity.

Keywords

Breast cancer, immunomodulation, ionic liquid, pentacyclic triterpene

Introduction

Terpenes and terpenoids, secondary plant metabolites, show great promise as drugs, drug additives, and food

preservatives (Brahmkshatriya and Brahmkshatriya 2013; Masyita et al. 2022). Betulinic acid (BA), a lupane-type triterpene, is one such promising lead compound in pharmaceutical development. It exhibits diverse biological

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activities *in vitro*, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antiviral, and anticancer properties (Lou et al. 2021; Oliveira-Costa et al. 2022). However, as with many other bioactive natural compounds, the large-scale production, purification, and stability of BA present major challenges. Furthermore, its poor water solubility, limited bioavailability, and long elimination half-life hinder its development as a therapeutic agent. *In vivo* studies have shown that BA is poorly absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract, with less than 1% of an orally administered dose reaching the systemic circulation (Furtado et al. 2017).

In recent years, the development of advanced BA formulations has become a key area of research to overcome these limitations. Notably, nanolipid-based systems have been shown to increase the oral bioavailability of BA by up to 17-fold in rat models (Ochoa-Rodríguez et al. 2025). Various nanocarrier platforms, including polymeric nanoparticles, liposomes, micelles, inorganic carriers, and hybrid systems, have improved targeted BA delivery in breast cancer models by enhancing solubility, stability, and intracellular accumulation (Morparia et al. 2024; Selepe et al. 2025). These formulations often increase the anticancer potency of BA, as evidenced by increased mitochondrial damage, reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, and apoptosis. However, the *in vivo* use of BA nanocarriers remains limited due to the complexity of their synthesis, dependence on external activation triggers, challenges in scaling up production, potential long-term toxicity, and poorly understood pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics (Alshawwa et al. 2022).

The anti-breast cancer activity of BA has been extensively investigated, and it has been shown that its cytotoxicity, similar to that of other natural compounds, arises from targeting multiple molecular pathways. These pathways include the suppression of cyclin and topoisomerase activities, the activation of mitochondrial-mediated apoptosis, the inhibition of NF- κ B signaling and Sp transcription factors, and the display of antiangiogenic actions (Salvador et al. 2014; Luo et al. 2016; Farooqi et al. 2022). Additionally, BA acts on more specific targets, such as estrogen receptors and multidrug resistance proteins. It has also been reported to display synergistic effects when combined with conventional chemotherapeutic agents (Zhang et al. 2015). Multi-target drugs offer several advantages, including a reduced likelihood of drug–drug interactions, wider therapeutic effectiveness in specific clinical contexts, improved patient convenience, and simplified treatment overall (Talevi 2015).

Another prospective strategy for overcoming issues associated with conventional solid-state drugs, such as polymorphism and poor solubility in biofluids, is to convert active pharmaceutical ingredients into ionic liquid (IL) or organic salt formulations (Stoimenovski et al. 2010; Shamshina et al. 2023). This could also suggest alternative routes of administration (Egorova et al. 2017). Additionally, the tunable combination of cation and anion in ILs provides a flexible platform for adjusting the physicochemical properties, stability, and biological activity of the target compound. However, only a few IL-based BA formulations have been investigated thus far. For example, trihexyltetradecylphos-

onium betulinatate exhibits the same cytotoxic effect on liver cancer cells as BA but is up to 6.3 times more selective for cancer cells than normal fibroblasts (Silva et al. 2019). However, compared to BA, its cholinium and benzalkonium salts exhibited 2–4.5 times higher cytotoxicity toward A375 melanoma cells, SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells, MCF-7 breast adenocarcinoma cells, and A431 epidermoid carcinoma cells (Suresh et al. 2012). Interestingly, incorporating a triphenylphosphonium moiety into BA via short-chain linkers and stabilizing it as a bromide resulted in anticancer activity up to 100 times stronger than BA when tested across nine different cell lines (Suárez-Rozas et al. 2025).

Recently, promising results were obtained with a series of BA-derived ILs containing biocompatible amino acid ethyl esters as counterions (Ossowicz-Rupniewska et al. 2024). These betulinates exhibited distinct physicochemical properties, including variations in water solubility and cytotoxicity toward two breast cancer cell lines: the hormone-dependent MCF-7 cells and the hormone-independent, highly invasive MDA-MB-231 cells. Among them, L-lysine ethyl ester bis(betulinatate) [LysOEt][BA]₂ displayed the greatest water solubility, indicating improved bioavailability potential. It produced modest increases in cytotoxicity: 2.3-fold in MCF-7 cells and 1.3-fold in MDA-MB-231 cells (Ossowicz-Rupniewska et al. 2024; Apostolova et al. 2025). However, the effects of BA-derived ILs on pathways related to metastasis, invasion, and stress responses remain largely unexplored.

To conduct a more thorough preclinical evaluation of the anti-breast cancer potency of [LysOEt][BA]₂, the research was expanded to include pathways that play a pivotal role in breast cancer invasion, metastasis, and resistance to therapy. Specifically, the effect of the IL on the activity of matrix metalloproteinases 2 and 9 (MMP-2 and MMP-9), endopeptidases collectively known as gelatinases, which are strongly linked to extracellular matrix degradation and metastatic spread in breast cancer, was examined (Khan et al. 2021). Oxidative stress responses in the highly invasive MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell line were also examined.

Because the dysregulated production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-6 and TNF- α , contributes to tumor progression and cancer-associated inflammation, their levels were assessed in stimulated peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) to determine whether the IL modulates immune-driven inflammatory responses relevant to cancer progression. The overall aim was to determine the effects of [LysOEt][BA]₂ on these processes in breast cancer cells and immune cells.

Materials and methods

Materials

Betulinic acid ($\geq 98\%$), high-glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) with 4,500 mg/L glucose, L-glutamine, sodium pyruvate, and sodium bicarbonate; RPMI-1640 medium with 20 mM HEPES and

L-glutamine; trypsin-EDTA solution; fetal bovine serum (FBS); penicillin-streptomycin solution (100×); gelatin type A; lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from *Escherichia coli*; and TRI Reagent were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. 2',7'-Dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA) and 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) stain were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific, as was the RevertAid First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit. L-lysine ethyl ester bis(betulinat) [LysOEt][BA]₂ was synthesized as previously reported (Ossowicz-Rupniewska et al. 2024). The human breast carcinoma MDA-MB-231 cell line was obtained from ATCC. The Precision Plus Protein Kaleidoscope standards and the Quick Start Bradford protein assay kit were obtained from Bio-Rad. The IL-6 ELISA kit was obtained from Elabscience (USA), and the TNF-α detection kit was obtained from DiaSource (Belgium).

Methods

Cell culturing

MDA-MB-231 cells (ATCC) were cultured in complete high-glucose DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and an antibiotic mixture containing penicillin (10,000 U/mL) and streptomycin (10 mg/mL). The cultures were maintained at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂ incubator and passaged every 2–3 days. The cells were used for experiments during the growth phase, when they reached 70–80% confluence.

Measurement of intracellular ROS levels

Intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels were quantified using the fluorescent probe DCFH-DA. MDA-MB-231 cells were seeded in 96-well plates and allowed to adhere overnight in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. The cells were then treated with BA or [LysOEt][BA]₂ at final concentrations of 6.25, 12.5, 25, or 50 μM for 6 h.

After treatment, the medium was removed, and the cells were incubated with serum-free DMEM containing 10 μM DCFH-DA for 30 min at 37 °C in the dark. After incubation, 10 μL of a 1 μg/mL DAPI solution was added to each well, and the plate was incubated for an additional 5 min in the dark. The cells were then washed twice with 100 μL of serum-free DMEM and once with 100 μL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). DCF (oxidized) fluorescence was quantified per well and normalized to DAPI fluorescence (DCFH-DA/DAPI). Acquisition settings were kept identical across groups, and background fluorescence from the probe-only and compound-only controls was subtracted.

Fluorescence intensity was measured using a CLARIOstar multimode plate reader with excitation/emission settings of 480/525 nm for DCF. DAPI fluorescence (excitation: 350 nm; emission: 460 nm) was used for normalization. Fluorescent images were acquired using a ZOE™ Fluorescent Cell Imager.

ROS levels in the treated groups were compared with those in the untreated control cells. Data are presented as the mean ± standard deviation (SD) from four independent experiments.

Effect of BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ on MMP-2 and MMP-9 activity in MDA-MB-231 cells

The cells were then treated with BA or [LysOEt][BA]₂ at a final concentration of 12.5 μM for 24 h in serum-free DMEM. After incubation, the culture supernatant was collected and concentrated using Vivaspin 500 centrifugal concentrators at 12,000 rpm for 20 min. Protein concentrations were determined using the Bradford assay according to the reagent manufacturer's protocol.

Gelatin zymography was performed as described by Bencsik et al. (2017), using 7.5% SDS-polyacrylamide gels containing 0.2% type A gelatin.

Briefly, 20 μL of cell lysate was mixed with nonreducing sample buffer and resolved on an SDS-polyacrylamide gel using a Tris-glycine running buffer at 4 °C on a Bio-Rad electrophoresis system. After electrophoresis, the gel was washed in an enzyme-renaturing buffer solution containing 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 2.5% Triton X-100, 5 mM CaCl₂, 5 mM MgCl₂, and 1 μM ZnCl₂ for 30 min at room temperature to remove SDS. The gels were then incubated in a developing buffer solution (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.8; 200 mM NaCl; 5 mM CaCl₂) for 30 min, followed by an additional 20-h incubation at 37 °C.

The gel was stained with 0.5% Coomassie Brilliant Blue R-250 in a solution of 50% methanol and 10% glacial acetic acid for 30 min. The gel was then destained until clear zones of gelatin degradation appeared against a dark blue background. Protein standards were run in parallel to estimate molecular weights based on relative mobility. The zymogram was scanned at 600 dpi using a BenQ Scanner 5000 with MiraScan 6.1 software in reflective mode.

MMP activity was identified by the presence of two characteristic bands: a slower-migrating MMP-9 homodimer (approximately 220 kDa) and a faster-migrating MMP-2 (approximately 62 kDa).

Isolation and culture of PBMCs

PBMCs were isolated from whole blood obtained from healthy volunteers using standard density-gradient centrifugation. The cells were cultured *in vitro* in the presence of BA or [LysOEt][BA]₂ at final concentrations of 2.5, 5, 10, or 20 μM. The cells were then incubated for either 6 h or 24 h at 37 °C in RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with 20 mM HEPES, L-glutamine, and 5% FBS. Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from *Escherichia coli* at a final concentration of 1 μg/mL was used as a positive stimulation control. Untreated cells (N) served as the negative control. Informed consent was obtained from all participants in accordance with the ethical standards of the Helsinki Declaration. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Medical Faculty, Trakia University, Stara Zagora, Bulgaria (Decision No. 23/10.03.2023).

Gene expression analysis (qPCR)

For the gene expression analysis, PBMCs were stimulated for 6 h at 37 °C with the indicated concentrations (5 μM and 10 μM). Total RNA was extracted using TRI

Reagent according to the manufacturer's protocol. RNA concentration and purity were then assessed spectrophotometrically. Complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesized from 1 µg of RNA using a RevertAid First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit and random hexamer primers.

Quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) was performed on a 7500 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems) using TaqMan inventoried assays for the target genes IL6 and TNFA and the reference genes β 2-microglobulin and GAPDH. Thermocycling conditions included an initial step at 95 °C for 10 min, followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 15 s and annealing/extension at 60 °C for 1 min.

Gene expression levels were normalized to the reference genes, and relative quantification was calculated using the Δ Ct method. Results are reported as the fold change relative to the calibrator group (untreated cells).

Cytokine quantification

The levels of the cytokines TNF- α and IL-6 in the culture supernatants were measured after 24 h using ELISA following the manufacturer's instructions. The sensitivity of the IL-6 ELISA kit (Elabscience, USA) was 0.94 pg/mL, and that of the TNF- α ELISA kit (DiaSource, Belgium) was 0.7 pg/mL. The cytokine levels were expressed in picograms per milliliter (pg/mL). The cytokine levels were presented as medians with interquartile range (IQR). A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for comparisons between groups.

Results and discussion

Effect of [LysOEt][BA]₂ on ROS levels and gelatinase activity in MDA-MB-231 cells

Intrinsic ROS play a complex and well-established role in cancer. At controlled or moderately elevated levels, ROS promote tumor progression by enhancing cell proliferation, motility, invasion, angiogenesis, and resistance to therapy. However, when ROS accumulate beyond a critical threshold, they induce oxidative stress, which ultimately triggers cell death (Nakamura and Takada 2021; Muchtaridi et al. 2024).

The effects of BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ on the overall redox imbalance in MDA-MB-231 cells were evaluated after 6 h of treatment at four concentrations: below the IC₅₀ (6.25 and 12.5 µM), around the IC₅₀ (25 µM), and above the 72-h IC₅₀ (50 µM). Previously reported 72-h IC₅₀ values were 43 µM for BA and 32 µM for [LysOEt][BA]₂ (Apostolova et al. 2025). Fig. 1 shows that treatment with BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ results in a concentration-dependent increase in intracellular ROS in MDA-MB-231 cells.

Interestingly, BA induces only moderate oxidative stress at the highest tested concentration, whereas at lower concentrations the effect is negligible. In contrast, the BA-IL formulation produces a much stronger effect, with increased ROS production observed even at the lowest

tested concentrations. No visible changes were detected after a longer incubation time (24 h). Similar pro-oxidant and pro-apoptotic effects have been reported in MDA-MB-231 cells treated with other plant-derived metabolites, including polyphenols, flavonoids, citrus glycoproteins, carotenoids, and others (Thangam et al. 2014; Martino et al. 2019; Slika et al. 2022; Wei et al. 2024). The results are consistent with previous observations showing an approximately twofold increase in intrinsic ROS generation in MDA-MB-231 cells treated with 20 µM Alisol B, a triterpenoid compound isolated from *Alisma orientale*, a traditional Chinese medicinal herb (Zhang et al. 2017).

Since ROS can regulate MMP expression and influence tumor invasiveness, it was evaluated whether BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ alter MMP-2 and MMP-9 activity in MDA-MB-231 cells. Lysate-derived MMP-2 and MMP-9 were clearly distinguished and identified based on their molecular weights using electrophoresis. A clear reduction in cell-associated MMP-2 activity (62 kDa) was observed in treated cells, with a slightly stronger effect for [LysOEt][BA]₂ (Fig. 2). A second distinct band displaying gelatinolytic activity corresponding to a protein of approximately 220 kDa, consistent with MMP-9 homodimers, was also detected.

The 2.5-fold decrease in intracellular MMP-2 activity indicates strong suppression of the proteolytic machinery associated with cell invasion. This suggests that the treatments, particularly [LysOEt][BA]₂, may effectively impair the invasive potential of MDA-MB-231 cells. In contrast, the effect of BA and its IL on MMP-9 activity is negligible. This finding aligns with the documented reduction in MMP-2 and MMP-9 activity in MDA-MB-231 cells treated with ursolic acid derivatives. However, the effect was stronger on MMP-9 in that case (Michalak et al. 2023). Additionally, Lou et al. observed inhibited MMP-2 and MMP-9 expression by the triterpene Alisol A in MDA-MB-231 cells (Lou et al. 2019).

Taken together, the data indicate that BA and its IL induce substantial redox stress and attenuate key proteolytic pathways associated with cell invasion. This led to further examination of their immunomodulatory properties.

Gene expression of TNFA and IL6 mRNA in PBMCs stimulated with BA or [LysOEt][BA]₂

Fig. 3 shows the relative expression of TNFA and IL6 mRNA. Stimulation of PBMCs with LPS induced a strong upregulation of both cytokines. IL6 exhibited a higher response (approximately 78-fold) than TNFA (approximately 27.5-fold), relative to untreated cells (N).

All tested compounds significantly suppressed IL6 expression compared with the LPS control. [LysOEt][BA]₂ demonstrated a clear dose-dependent reduction in IL6 mRNA levels. The higher concentration (10 µM) resulted in a statistically significant decrease in IL6 expression compared with the 5 µM concentration, reducing IL6 expression to a level comparable to that of untreated cells.

Figure 1. Fluorescence microscopy images of intracellular ROS generation in MDA-MB-231 cells, as indicated by DCFH-DA fluorescence, after 6 h of treatment with BA (A: 6.25 μM; B: 12.5 μM; C: 25.0 μM; D: 50.0 μM) and with [LysOEt][BA]₂ (E: 6.25 μM; F: 12.5 μM; G: 25.0 μM; H: 50.0 μM). I: untreated cells (control). J: fold increase in DCF fluorescence (ROS generation) normalized to cell number. Data are presented as mean ± SD from four independent experiments.

Figure 2. Effect of [LysOEt][BA]₂ and BA on MMP-2 and MMP-9 expression in MDA-MB-231 cells, assessed by gelatin zymography of cell lysates after 24 h of treatment.

Figure 3. Relative expression (fold change, log scale) of TNFA and IL6 mRNA in PBMCs stimulated with betulinic acid and [LysOEt][BA]₂. PBMCs were cultured with 1 µg/mL LPS or with BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ at final concentrations of 5 µM and 10 µM. The results were normalized to untreated cells (N) and are presented as mean and standard errors of the relative expression (fold change) on a logarithmic scale. Note: *, ** - $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$ compared with LPS-treated cells. ^, ^^ - $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$ compared with BA-treated cells with the same concentration.

In contrast, TNFA expression exhibited a biphasic response to [LysOEt][BA]₂. At 5 µM, [LysOEt][BA]₂ increased TNFA expression approximately 55-fold, exceeding the levels observed in untreated and LPS-stimulated cells. However, at 10 µM, TNFA expression decreased sharply, returning to a level similar to that observed in the LPS control. These results suggest a concentration-dependent reversal of the effect.

TNF-α and IL-6 secretion levels

Significant reductions in TNF-α and IL-6 secretion were observed for all tested compounds compared with cells stimulated with LPS alone, even at the lowest concentration of 2.5 µM. IL-6 levels followed a suppressive trend similar to that of TNF-α levels.

LPS stimulation resulted in high median TNF-α levels of 318.7 pg/mL (interquartile range [IQR]: 156.9–526). Treatment with BA and its derivatives drastically reduced these levels. Fig. 4A specifically shows that BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ maintain median TNF-α levels below 100 pg/mL across concentrations ranging from 2.5 to 20 µM, which is comparable to the untreated control (N).

LPS stimulation markedly increased IL-6 production, yielding a median concentration of 2994.5 pg/mL (IQR: 2164.7–3451.7). Treatment with BA and its derivatives clearly reduced IL-6 secretion in a dose-dependent manner (Fig. 4B). At the lowest tested concentration (2.5 µM), BA (median: 523.25 pg/mL) and [LysOEt][BA]₂ (median: 223.54 pg/mL) elicited reductions in IL-6 levels relative to LPS-stimulated cells of more than fivefold. Additionally, [LysOEt][BA]₂ exhibited the strongest inhibitory effect. Across the entire concentration range (2.5–20 µM), IL-6 concentrations were substantially suppressed, approaching the levels observed in untreated cells.

Recent reviews confirm that BA exerts its broad anti-inflammatory effects primarily by inhibiting the NF-κB signaling pathway, mainly by blocking the phosphorylation and subsequent degradation of IκB, preventing the translocation of the active NF-κB subunit (p65) to the nucleus, and influencing the transcription of pro-inflammatory genes, including IL6 and TNFA (Oliveira-Costa et al. 2022).

Figure 4. Effect of BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ on TNF-α (A) and IL-6 (B) secretion in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs). PBMCs were cultured for 24 h with 1 µg/mL LPS or with BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ at final concentrations of 2.5 µM, 5 µM, 10 µM and 20 µM. Cytokine concentration in the supernatant was measured by ELISA. The results are presented as the median and interquartile range (IQR) and compared using the Mann-Whitney test. Note: *, ** - $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$ compared with LPS-treated cells. ^ - $p < 0.05$; ^^ - $p < 0.01$ compared with BA-treated cells with the same concentration.

Several studies affirm the pleiotropic role of IL-6 in breast cancer, encompassing proliferation, immune evasion, metastasis, and inflammation maintenance in the tumor microenvironment. The IL-6/JAK/STAT3 signaling axis is frequently activated in breast cancer and is strongly linked to metastasis involving the upregulation of MMP-2 and MMP-9 (Manore et al. 2022). By potentially inhibiting IL-6 production, [LysOEt][BA]₂ exhibits a mechanism by which it may indirectly suppress metastatic potential, further confirming the multitarget and multilevel effects characteristic of natural products.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that both BA and its ionic liquid derivative [LysOEt][BA]₂ exhibit complex anticancer and anti-inflammatory effects. The IL formulation is consistently more potent. In MDA-MB-231 cells, [LysOEt][BA]₂ induces a significant, dose-dependent increase in intracellular ROS levels, surpassing the mild oxidative response elicited by BA. This enhanced redox stress correlates with a significant decrease in MMP-2 activity, indicating the effective suppression of proteolytic pathways that promote extracellular matrix degradation and tumor cell invasion. Although MMP-9 activity remained largely unchanged, the strong inhibition of MMP-2 indicates a targeted impact on invasive potential.

In immune cells, both BA and [LysOEt][BA]₂ significantly attenuate TNF- α and IL-6 cytokine responses. The IL formulation robustly suppressed IL6 mRNA expression and secretion in a dose-dependent manner, approaching the levels observed in untreated cells. Despite the biphasic modulation of TNFA transcription, TNF- α secretion was uniformly reduced across all treatments, indicating a net anti-inflammatory effect.

Taken together, these findings suggest that [LysOEt][BA]₂ increases the biological activity of BA. This occurs through promoting oxidative stress-mediated anticancer responses, impairing invasion-associated MMP-2 activity, and suppressing key pro-inflammatory cytokines. This dual action on cancer and immune cells indicates that BA-derived ionic liquids have the potential to be developed further as multifunctional anticancer agents.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Informed consent was obtained from all participants in accordance with the ethical standards of the Helsinki Declaration. The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Medical Faculty, Trakia University, Stara Zagora, Bulgaria (Decision number №23/10.03.2023).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: MDA-MB-231 cells (ATCC HTB-26)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization (MG, LM), Methodology (MG, LM), Formal analysis (MG, LM), Investigation (MG, YR, LM, AG, ND, POR), Data Curation (MG, LM), Writing - Original draft (MG, LM), Writing - Review and Editing (MG, LM, POR).

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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